

THE NEW GENERATION OF COMPOSITE MEMBRANES FOR OPHTHALMOLOGY APPLICATION

E. Stodolak^{1*}, J. Wieczorek², T. Gumula¹, S. Blazewicz¹, R. Leszczynski³

¹ Department of Biomaterials, Faculty of Materials Science and Ceramics, University of Science and Technology, Krakow, Poland, *e-mail: stodolak@agh.edu.pl

² Department of Biotechnology of Animal Reproduction, National Research Institute of Animal Production, Balice, Poland

³ Department of Ophthalmology, Medical University of Silesia, Katowice, Poland

SUMMARY

The new generation of biomaterials designed for intracorneal ophthalmologic implants was invented and produced. This biocompatible biomaterial exhibits specific biomechanical parameters, which enable its use as an ophthalmologic implant.

Keywords: composite membrane, glaucoma implant, sodium alginate

INTRODUCTION

Glaucoma is a group of eye diseases that lead to damage of the optic nerve which then can lead to vision loss and possible blindness. The optic nerve damage occurs due to excessive intraocular pressure. Most patients with glaucoma require only medications to control the eye pressure. When medicine therapy fails to lower the pressure a surgery is required. Such treatments often involve use of lasers or utilization of membrane implants. The objective of any glaucoma surgery is to enable the eye fluid to circulate within the eye more easily. Worldwide, it is estimated that about 6.8 million people have visual impairment from glaucoma, and 6.7 million suffer from blindness [1]. The main role of implants in glaucoma treatment is to decrease pressure inside the eye, by improving aqueous humor flow from inside of an eye ball. Such membrane implants should facilitate its filtration [2-3].

Materials used for ophthalmologic implants should fulfil such criteria as; biocompatibility, biostability and suitable porosity [4-5], and typically they belong to two groups, i.e.; natural polymers, e.g. collagen, hiauronians or synthetic polymers, e.g. e-PTFE, PP, silicones. The main problems concerning resorbable membranes (collagen, hiauronians) is their instability and low permeability [6]. On the other hand, such materials are characterised with good biocompatibility, and can very well mimic structures of natural tissues. For a long-term use, the materials applied for cornea implants have to withstand static and dynamic pressure changes, and also have to be stable in biological environment. Therefore, their durability in *in vitro* conditions plays a very important role [7]. The equally important parameters of an ophthalmologic membrane are porosity, and mean pores size and related to them its permeability. Too small pores can be easily blocked by molecules present in aqueous humor, while big pores may undergo deformation due to high intraocular pressures [7-8].

The aim of this work was to prepare biocompatible composite membrane that can be used in glaucoma treatment. Microstructure, mechanical parameters and biocompatibility of the material were optimized, and the effect of simulated biological environment on the membrane materials was investigated. The membrane was made of a stable synthetic polymer, i.e. PTFE-PVDF-PP, which was a composite matrix, and a fibrous phase consisting of sodium alginate, which was a porogene responsible for creation of desired porosity in the polymer matrix. The investigations consisted in preparation and characterisation of the membrane materials which physicochemical properties and microstructure were similar to the properties of the tissue which would be its future implantation place.

Materials and methods

PTFE-PVDF-PP terpolymer (Aldrich Chemical Co., USA) and sodium alginate (Biopolymer, AS Protanal LF 20/60, with dominating blocs of guluronic acid, ~ 65 %, Norway) were used to prepare composite membranes. Two types of composite materials were made. The first type of composites was prepared by using 2 wt. % of sodium alginate (NA) in the form of a powder. The second type of composite samples was prepared by using 2 wt. % of sodium alginate in the form of two-fraction additive, i.e. short fibres and small particles. The two-fraction additive was prepared by grinding of short alginate fibres in a rotating mill. The aim of the fibres fragmentation was to improve their ability to create a continuous network in the composite and subsequently similar network of pores in the membranes. In order to make pores in the material, sodium alginate was removed from composite by immersing the samples in aqueous sodium chloride solution, which led to dissolving of sodium alginate, and subsequently to samples with controlled porosity.

The porogene morphology, i.e. sodium alginate fibres/particles, was observed with electron scanning microscope (SEM, Jeol 5400). Particle size distribution of the powder was determined by DLS method (Nanosizer-ZS), and fibres size (diameter, length) was measured with optical microscope (Lanametr, PZO, Poland). Weighted amounts of the porogene (2 wt.%) were mixed with the polymer solution. Then such mixture was poured on a Petri dish, and dried at ambient temperature for 48h in order to evaporate the solvent, which led to material in the form of thin foils. In order to create open porosity within the materials, the porogene was removed by incubation of the polymer foils in distilled water at 80°C for 84h. During this treatment dissolving and washing-out of NA took place. Using this method two kinds of membranes were produced; **M1** – membrane derived from composite containing only NA particles, **M2** - membrane derived from composite containing NA fibres and particles which were products of their fragmentation (grinding). Morphology of the membranes was investigated with scanning electron microscope (SEM, Jeol 5400).

Permeability of the membranes in static *in vitro* conditions was tested, by measuring electrolytic conductivity of distilled water separated by the membrane from NaCl solution (0.1M NaCl/37⁰C/3 weeks).

Permeability of the membranes in dynamic *in vitro* conditions was investigated using unique apparatus which simulated pressure conditions the eye (Fig.4). The eye simulator was designed to compare changes of intraocular pressure in a normal eye, with the pressure in eye with glaucoma disease. During the investigations, the apparatus

was set to simulate pressure conditions taking place during severe attack of glaucoma, i.e. the cyclic pressure exerted on the membrane was 55 mmHg (5h/37°C).

As a biological environment a bovine serum modified with 5% of albumins was used. Similarly like in a case of the static conditions, the membrane was placed between two chambers – one filled with distilled water and the second one filled with the serum.

The permeability was determined by means of measurements of the ionic conductivity of the serum. After testing in the eye simulator, microstructure, sample thickness were measured. Mechanical properties of the composite samples and membranes, e.g. tensile strength, Young's modulus, elongation to break, maximum force and fracture work, were measured using a universal testing machine Zwick 1435.

Results

Microscope observations of sodium alginate short fibres after grinding (fragmentation) in a laboratory rotating mill indicated that the fibrous phase consisted from short fibres (diameter of $0.17 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{m}$, length of $1.50 \pm 0.28 \text{ mm}$; 95 % of population), and much smaller particles (diameter of $0.75 \mu\text{m}$; 5 % of population), which were products of their fragmentation (Fig.1). Diversification of the porogene particles sizes ensures formation of network of interconnected pores of sizes equal to the porogene fibres and products of their fragmentation. The alginate powder used as a porogene in the other membrane type consisted of particles with similar sizes (Fig.1, diameter $0.45 \div 0.75 \mu\text{m}$), which were origin of pores of analogous characteristics.

Figure 1. Morphology of the applied porogenes; sodium alginate fibres (NA), sodium alginate powder (NA)

The membranes produced via removal of the porogene, despite its form (powder or fibres), exhibited surface porosity and similar thickness of about 180 – 200 μm . M1 membrane, which was derived from alginate fibres and products of their fragmentation, exhibited two populations of pores, i.e. large, elliptical pores (washed out fibres, small amount) and small, round pores (washed out products of the fibres fragmentation, larger amount). Cross-sections of the membranes revealed, that the presence of pores was not only limited to the membrane surface, but they were also present in its bulk (Fig.2). A system of the interconnected pores is particularly visible in a case of M2 membrane, in which porogene consisted of mixture of fibres and particles with different size.

Figure 2. SEM microstructure of surface of membrane materials; M1 – membrane derived from NA powder, M2 – membrane derived from NA fibres and powder

Analysis of the microphotographs revealed, that both membranes had similar porosity, which was slightly higher in a case of M1 membrane (c.a. 54%), than in a case of M2 membrane (c.a. 49%). Higher porosity of the first membrane derived from alginate powder was a result of washing out of the porogene from the polymer matrix. Removal of the fibrous phase in the applied conditions required longer incubation time. The mean size of pores visible on the membrane surface was close to the size of the removed porogene and was equal to c.a. 25 μm and c.a. 15 μm for M1, and M2 membrane, respectively. The pores had sizes suitable for macromolecules present in aqueous humor, i.e. proteins such as albumin, and inorganic salts.

Measurements of changes of electrolytic conductivity of distilled water which was separated by the membrane from NaCl solution confirmed that the membranes were permeable for ions. A test performed in static conditions revealed that Na^+ , and Cl^- ions migrated more rapidly through M1 membrane, which could be related to its bigger pore size, or better developed network of interconnecting pores (Fig.3).

Figure 3. Permeability test of the membranes in static conditions (0.1M NaCl/37⁰C/3 weeks). Changes of the ionic conductivity of distilled water separated from NaCl solution by a membrane

Permeability of the membranes was investigated in dynamic *in vitro* conditions using unique equipment which simulated the eye (Fig.4). Filtration and micro-filtration proceeded despite the body fluid (bovine serum) contained simple proteins, i.e. albumins. Despite relatively high pressure exerted on the membranes in the apparatus, they did not lose their permeability, which indicates that the pores were not blocked with the protein molecules, and the liquid circulation was not disturbed. Also the ion conductivity of solution used to test permeability remained at the same level during whole time of the experiment (Fig.4). Stability of the curve in both of liquids: water and bovine serum confirmed stably flux by membranes.

Both investigated membrane materials were stable in *in vitro* conditions, since no degradation of the materials took place, i.e. no chemical and physical changes were observed after 24 months of incubation in water at 37⁰C. The results indicated that the membrane materials may be successfully applied as long term implants in glaucoma treatment.

membrane - M1

membrane – M2

Figure 4. Permeability of membrane; M1 and M2 during flux by membrane in dynamic condition (water/37°C/7 days, or bovine serum/37°C/7 days)

As it could be expected, the membrane materials showed inferior mechanical properties in comparison with pure polymer foil (the reference sample). In case of the membranes, decrease of tensile strength (R_m), Young's modulus (E), and work to break (W), and maximum elongation (ϵF_{max}) was observed, Table 1. These changes resulted from higher porosity of the membrane materials.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of membrane materials: M1 and M2

Material	R_m [MPa]	ϵF_{max} [%]	E [MPa]	W [J]
Membrane M1	0.28 ± 0.06	258.42 ± 39.48	0.12 ± 0.06	0.217 ± 0.06
Membrane M2	0.35 ± 0.02	485.17 ± 45.24	0.19 ± 0.04	0.369 ± 0.08
Polymer foil	0.5 ± 0.06	726.32 ± 53.12	0.49 ± 0.14	0.409 ± 0.03

Test performed on the membranes subjected to a constant load indicated, that despite considerable deterioration of the mechanical properties of the materials, the size and shape of pores did not change. Also the membrane thickness remained stable i.e. 180 – 200 μm . Changes of microstructure of the membranes under the applied load were so small, that they did not influence their permeability.

The last stage of the investigations was testing of the membranes' work endurance in conditions of static or dynamic load. Both tests were performed in load conditions exceeding the ones present in an eye with glaucoma disease. Results of the tests indicated, that both membranes were slightly worn after the work. Changes observed on their surfaces were related to shape and size of the pores. The average diameter of pores was bigger than in non-loaded materials, i.e. 30-35 μm , and 35-40 μm in case of M1 and M2 membrane, respectively. Neither of the membranes was broken nor damaged during the mechanical test.

Summary

Application of fibres for polymer modification is a useful method for preparation of functionalised membrane material. The best mechanical characteristic had the material based on sodium alginate fibres, which exhibited the highest elongation to break and tensile strength. The membranes are stable in *in vitro* conditions. No degradation of the material was observed, i.e. any chemical and physical changes took place.

Taking into account conditions of the performed investigations, it may be stated that both types of membranes were characterised by relatively high strength and elasticity. Due to these features, their mechanical properties should remain stable after their implantation. Extreme conditions of the tests did not lead to damage of any membrane material, which enables to presume that such membrane is suitable for a long-term performance implant.

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